

Conformation analyses of *N*-(3-pyridyl)-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamine

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N-(3-Pyridyl)-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamine (**1**) has been studied by AM1 and PM3 semi-empirical quantum mechanical methods. Minimum energy conformation from AM1 and PM3 are calculated as a function of θ (C10-C11-N1-C12). Tautomerism and tautomer conformations of the compound (**1**) have also been investigated by AM1 and PM3 semi-empirical quantum mechanical calculations and found that the non-planar conformation is the most stable conformation in all calculations.

Most molecular properties such as electron energy levels, electron population in chemical bonds, electronegativity, and dipole moments can be derived from molecular orbital calculations. In this study, a tautomeric properties of the Schiff base ligand *N*-(3-pyridyl)-2-oxo-1-naphthylidene-methylamine (**1**) have been investigated by using AM1 and PM3 semi-empirical quantum mechanical calculations. 2-Hydroxy Schiff base ligands and their complexes derived from the reaction of salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with amines have been extensively studied¹⁻³. Tautomerism in 2-hydroxy Schiff bases both in solution and in solid state was investigated using spectroscopy²⁻⁴. 2-Hydroxy Schiff base ligands are of interest mainly due to the existence of O-H...N and O...H-N type hydrogen bonds and tautomerism between enol and keto forms. The hydrogen bonding, tautomerism of Schiff bases and the tautomeric forms at 50% abundance have been reported in the crystalline state of the Schiff base formed by 2-aminopyridine and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde².

Results and Discussion

The crystal structure of *N*-(3-pyridyl)-2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamine (**1**) (C₁₆H₁₂N₂O) (Fig. 1)⁵ was solved by SHELXS-97⁶ and refined SHELXS-97⁷. Geometry optimization of compound **1** by the AM1 and PM3 methods implemented in the MOPAC package running on a PENTIUM II PC, was performed starting from its crystallographic coordinates with hydrogen atoms placed at a distance of 1.08 Å from their target C atoms or 0.93 Å for oxygen atoms.

In order to define the conformational flexibility of the title molecule (**1**), semi-empirical calculations using the AM1 and PM3 molecular orbital method, were carried out. Conformational calculations were performed with respect to the torsion angle of θ (C10-C11-N1-C12) which con-

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of compound **1**; displacement ellipsoids are plotted at the 50% probability level.

trols the planarity of **1**. To determine the conformational energy profiles the optimized geometry of the investigated compound was kept fixed, and values at the AM1 and PM3 energies were calculated as a function of the torsion angle θ (C10-C11-N1-C12) in steps of 5°. The AM1 and PM3 optimized geometry and conformations of compound **1** are in agreement with those crystallographically observed. The molecular energy can be divided into bonded and non-bonded contributions. The bonded energy is considered to be independent of torsion angle changes and therefore vanishes when relative conformer energies are calculated as in our calculations. The non-bonded energy (E_N) is then further separated into torsional (E_T), steric (E_S) and electrostatic (E_{ES}) contributions,

$$E_N = E_T + E_S + E_{ES} \quad (1)$$

where, the torsional energy (E_T) is that parts of the total energy which does not originate from the steric or electrostatic factors.

The bond lengths and angles of X-ray structure were

compared with those from AM1 and PM3 molecular orbital calculations. The results are given in Table 1 and illustrated in Figs. 2–4. Table 1 shows, that the bond length and angles found from AM1 are more consistent with those of X-ray structure than their PM3 counterparts. The heat of formation profile predicted by AM1 molecular orbital calculation on the X-ray structure is runs lower than its PM3 counter-

part throughout (Fig. 2). We have also performed the conformational analyses of enol and keto tautomeric forms of **1** using AM1 and PM3 semi-empirical molecular orbital methods. In all calculations, we found that the AM1 calculations

Table 1. Comparison of the bond lengths and bond angles for **1**

	X-ray	PM3	AM1
Bond Lengths (Å) :			
O(1)-C(1)	1.316(3)	1.3652110	1.3503428
C(1)-C(2)	1.424(3)	1.4323381	1.4308322
C(2)-C(3)	1.348(3)	1.3636035	1.3611968
C(3)-C(4)	1.424(3)	1.4254707	1.4255980
C(4)-C(5)	1.411(3)	1.4189047	1.4179581
C(5)-C(6)	1.365(4)	1.3745829	1.3703644
C(6)-C(7)	1.385(4)	1.4116816	1.4102901
C(7)-C(8)	1.365(3)	1.3754987	1.3704171
C(8)-C(9)	1.412(3)	1.4216712	1.4200963
C(9)-C(10)	1.448(3)	1.3921988	1.3967143
C(10)-C(11)	1.422(3)	1.4650667	1.4560028
C(11)-N(1)	1.301(3)	1.2940894	1.3038316
N(1)-C(12)	1.411(3)	1.4060709	1.4282949
C(12)-C(13)	1.393(3)	1.4250415	1.4042286
C(13)-N(2)	1.336(3)	1.3425467	1.3506057
N(2)-C(14)	1.333(3)	1.3468010	1.3523056
C(14)-C(15)	1.373(3)	1.4061685	1.3959991
C(15)-C(16)	1.378(3)	1.3918632	1.3897443
Bond angles (°) :			
O(1)-C(1)-C(2)	117.9(2)	112.688880	114.235683
C(1)-C(2)-C(3)	120.9(2)	120.063713	119.827279
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	121.9(2)	120.748891	120.779761
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	120.8(2)	120.298608	120.146602
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	120.7(2)	120.676252	120.488686
C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	119.4(2)	119.617383	119.929522
C(6)-C(7)-C(8)	121.6(2)	120.695529	120.455211
C(7)-C(8)-C(9)	121.1(2)	121.098093	121.000615
C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	123.5(2)	126.323151	124.610611
C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	121.5(2)	122.985385	122.141033
C(10)-C(11)-N(1)	122.3(2)	123.509358	119.628186
C(11)-N(1)-C(12)	122.2(2)	121.600614	122.898354
N(1)-C(12)-C(13)	123.3(2)	123.913154	123.345771
C(12)-C(13)-N(2)	124.0(2)	123.956487	121.075417
C(13)-N(2)-C(14)	126.7(2)	127.641961	119.987093
N(2)-C(14)-C(15)	123.6(2)	123.210232	121.491652
C(14)-C(15)-C(16)	129.2(2)	119.079992	119.440184

Fig. 2. AM1 and PM3 conformation energies of the X-ray as function of the θ (C10-C11-N1-C12) torsion angle (X-ray geometry used) : (■) PM3, (●) AM1.

predict higher stability than PM3 calculations. In the conformational energy profile of enol form there is one energy barrier near 170 (both AM1 and PM3) due to interaction between non-bonded C13 and O1 hydrogen atoms (1.03 Å) (Fig. 3). The position of energy barrier of the enol form **1** is consistent with the AM1 and PM3 calculations on the X-ray structure. In the keto form the locations of the energy barrier predicted by AM1 and PM3 are obviously distinct

Fig. 3. AM1 and PM3 conformation energies of the enol form as a function of the θ (C10-C11-N1-C12) torsion angle: (●) AM1-enol, (■) PM3-enol.

(Fig. 4). The energy barrier arises from the steric interactions between the non-bonded C13 and O1 hydrogen atoms. In all calculations the non-planar conformations are the most stable conformation. Semi-empirical AM1 calcu-

Fig. 4. AM1 and PM3 conformation energies of the keto form as a function of the θ (C10-C11-N1-C12) torsion angle: (●) AM1-keto, (■) PM3-keto.

lations show a good agreement between X-ray and enol structures. Bürgi and Dunitz⁸ carried out an extensive theoretical and experimental study on the non-planar conformation of *N*-benzylideneaniline and related compounds. Their statements regarding the non-planarity of *N*-benzylideneaniline refer to a competition between two principal factors: (i) the interaction of the *ortho* hydrogen on the aniline ring and the hydrogen on the bridge carbon is repulsive in the planar conformation but gets reduced with increasing non-planar-

ity, and (ii) the π -electron system, itself divisible into two components, including, on the one hand, delocalization between the -HC=N- double bond and the aniline phenyl ring (maximized for a planar conformation) and, on the other hand, delocalization of the nitrogen lone-pair of electrons into the aniline ring is essentially zero for the planar conformation but increase with increasing non-planarity (where the lone pair density on the nitrogen could interact with the π systems of the ring). The planar conformation is the most stable conformation for the enol form of 1. The repulsive interactions between non-bonded C13 and O1 hydrogen atoms are dominant when increasing the non-planarity of the enol form 1 increases.

References

1. M. Yildiz, Z. Kiliç and T. Hökelek, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1998, **441**, 1.
2. A. Elmali, *J. Chem. Crystallogr.*, 2000, **30**, 473.
3. J. Costamagna, J. Vargas, R. Latorre, A. Alvarado and G. Mena, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **119**, 67.
4. M. Gavranic, B. Kaitner and E. Mestrovic, *J. Chem. Crystallogr.*, 1996, **26**, 23.
5. L. J. Farrugia, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1997, **30**, 565.
6. G. M. Sheldrick, "SHELXS-97, Program for the Solution of Crystal Structures", University of Goettingen, Germany, 1997.
7. G. M. Sheldrick, "SHELXL-97, Program for the Refinement of Crystal Structures", University of Goettingen, Germany, 1997.
8. H. B. Bürgi and J. D. Dunitz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **54**, 1255.